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The Necessity of Reading Books in Protecting Young People from Information Attacks

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***Abstract:** No one can deny that the processes of globalization that took place at the world level in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries have created unprecedented opportunities for the development of all peoples and nations of the Earth, especially the younger generation. First of all, today we all witness that the advanced achievements of science and technology, modern information and communication technologies, in particular, the Internet system, open the borders between different countries and regions, make a great contribution to the development of mutual cooperation and integration.*

***Keywords:** struggle of ideas, information attacks, ideological pressure, self-perception of youth, evil vices corroding morality.*

It is known that today in the world there is an acute struggle and competition, the conflict of interests is intensifying. The processes of globalization create new opportunities for humanity, as well as unexpected problems. Threats and dangers to national identity and moral values are increasing. Thinking only about oneself, taking work and family lightly, consumerism is masterfully introduced into the minds of people, especially young people, in various ways. Every nation has its own traditions, customs and national values. The spiritual norms that originated in a particular land and have been shaped and refined over hundreds of years are the priceless wealth of that nation and people. A deeper understanding of the essence of such wealth becomes acutely important in the processes of globalization and technology that are rapidly entering our lives. "Mass culture" taking a sharp turn today is also one of the spiritual threats.

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witness that the advanced achievements of science and technology, modern information and communication technologies, in particular, the Internet system, open the borders between different countries and regions, make a great contribution to the development of mutual cooperation and integration.

Of course, our people, including the younger generation, do not deny the advanced aspects of Western science and technology, culture, literature. However, our youth need to quickly understand the spiritual and moral foundations of “mass culture”, which the progressive intellectuals of the West themselves assess as “the problem of the West”.

Today, in order to increase the interest of young people to read books, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 13, 2017 “On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publishing and distribution of book products, increase and popularize the culture of reading and reading books”, 2019 Decisions of June 7, 2016. “On Further Improvement of Information and Library Services to the Population of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, as well as one of the 5 important initiatives put forward by the President to raise the morale of young people and organize their free time in a meaningful way - to raise the morale of young people and spread reading among them. The program is implemented in our outreach activities¹.

It is noteworthy that, according to this draft document, in order to bring the development and support of reading culture in Uzbekistan to a new level, to develop effective solutions to infrastructural and educational system, problems related to reading, the National Program on the development of reading culture in Uzbekistan has been developed. development and support of reading culture for 2020-2025 and approved “Roadmap” for its implementation.

From the content of the tasks defined as priorities for the implementation of the program, it can be understood that the implementation of this draft document will further strengthen the work on the development of reading in our country.

Including

- Improvement of legal and regulatory documents and material and technical base for the development of reading culture;
- publishing quality books that meet, first of all, the spiritual-educational, artistic and aesthetic demands of our people.
- Determination of organizational measures;
- taking measures to radically improve the system of timely and affordable delivery of books to places and educational institutions;
- translation of the best examples of national and world literature, creation of legal bases for the organization of systematic work aimed at solving important issues related to the improvement of reading culture;
- definition of organizational measures aimed at uniting educational institutions and regional libraries on the basis of a centralized library - the “Unified Electronic Library” project;

¹ Dzhumaev E. Prevention of moral threats by increasing the culture of reading in the minds of young people. The role and relevance of social humanities in the formation of reading mindset among young people. Opposite. May 5-6. 2021. Pages 66-68.

- development of specific mechanisms aimed at the development of reading culture in regions and settlements;
- to ensure an increase in the share of young artists in the investments made in our country through the annual realization of innovative projects of young artists;

On this day, each pupil or student will tell the science teacher in detail about a fairy tale, short story, novel or poem they read last week. The points they receive in this process should be factored into the overall grading criteria.²

One of the biggest threats of social media to the stability of the family and society is that many peaceful families are destroyed because of their communication.

Every parent who wants a promising and bright future for their child should take the issue of education seriously. Young people should be educated not from various computer houses, internet and social networks, but first of all from parents, grandparents, good books that call for goodness, purity and religion.³

After all, fiction and books are the main means of enlightening society and saving people from ignorance. "Enlightenment is a person's emergence from the state of youthfulness left by his own fault. Minority is the inability to use one's own mind and intelligence without guidance from outside. Self-inflicted immaturity is not a lack of intelligence, but a lack of determination and courage, and an inability to use the mind without someone else's help. Sapere the helper! Use your mind with courage! - is the slogan of enlightenment⁴.

During the next two and a half years, our country is undergoing a process of intensive reforms. Attracting foreign investment into the economy and creating an active business environment are of great importance. In this sense, advanced book reading and popularization initiatives are being promoted in our country. These include:

- starting paper production in our country to make books cheaper;
- stimulating entrepreneurs engaged in bookselling; - organizing libraries in every micro-district;
- It is necessary to further develop the tradition of "nazm va navo" in such contests as "Best Book of the Year", "Book Family", "Best Children's Book", "Best Book Reader" and various cultural and educational events. That is, creating a wide opportunity for poets, writers, playwrights and scriptwriters from the arts to participate in such conferences will have a good effect;
- parents should regularly take their children to bookstores, encourage them to visit the library, encourage the establishment of family and private libraries, and widely publicize the tradition of book donation among the public⁵.

"Under certain difficulties of the transition period, a part of the young generation may form and decide that the main way to achieve a high standard of living is connected with illegal activities.⁶

² Tursunov S. What saves young people from the "Web"? <https://adolat.uz/news/nima-kutkaradiy> See More

³ Narzullaev O. Protection of youth from information attacks and ideological threats. May 28, 2021.

⁴ Kant I. Criticism is understandable. M., 1964. T. 3 -C. 85.

⁵ Y. Karimov. The role of fiction in protecting young people from information and psychological attacks. Vol. 2019 : Vol. 2, Article 19.

They are caused by mistakes and shortcomings in the upbringing of young people and the impoverishment of spirituality. Such a process occurs as a result of insufficient attention to the education of involvement in the process of formation of civil society. Spiritual impoverishment leads to a weakening of a person's attachment to his people, his homeland. The formation of ideological immunity, capable of resisting information attacks and destructive ideas, is also directly related to the level of involvement. Because the ideological immunity of an interested person will be strong. And the spirituality of a person with ideological immunity increases even more.⁷

In conclusion, we can say that the worldview, knowledge and attitude of young people to surrounding events are considered important factors that determine our tomorrow, our future, and books and reading are leading in this. After all, no one can mislead the reading public.

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⁶ K. Turaev. Development of leadership qualities in youth. Social activity of youth in modernizing society: collection of articles of the republican scientific-practical conference on the theme of problems and solutions - Tashkent: “Publishing house ‘Innovative Development’”, 2020. - 10 p

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